

Underneath the Cornfields: Digging into the Iowa Carbon Pipelines

Introduction

Several carbon pipelines have been proposed to be built in the State of Iowa, and were the subject of study in Associate Professor of Environmental Studies and Political Science Rachel Brummel's fall environmental justice and law course. Brummel's students analyzed various justice concerns ranging from local to intergenerational perspectives. From local procedural justice concerns to the potential hazardous disasters for future generations to contend with, the students' research supported their majority claim that the storage and transfer of carbon waste across Iowa and around the midwest presents exigent concerns for individual health, safety, and justice.

I. Justice on the Local Scale

Prepared by Sydney Frank, Jacob Hansen, Payton Lott, Salomé Valdivieso Santillán, Evan Turner, and Thomas Woodford

At a local level, Indigenous grassroots movements, such as the Great Plains Action, have successfully formed coalitions with unusual alliances such as white farm land owners. Since most of the resistance movement has been centered over private property rights in opposition to eminent domain, Indigenous activists have successfully joined this concern by highlighting the Indigenous belief in the commons and aligned values with regional and national campaigns against extractive energy, such as the Bekkel movement. Within this context, our understanding of how Indigenous Communities at a local level engage with carbon dioxide removal (CDR) projects has proven to be intertwined with a broader anticapitalist and anti-extractivist global movement.

Iowa's economy is entwined with ethanol and biofuel production. This industry has effectively positioned itself as a stepping stone to greener energy solutions. However, studies are unable to determine the real carbon cost of the lifecycle of ethanol. Opposing views from different government agencies, ethanol producers, and climate scientists leave many questions insufficiently answered. Despite this, it is impossible to argue that Iowa's land policies from the Homestead Acts to the Renewable Fuel Standards have caused the irreversible destruction of the world's largest prairie ecosystem and the release of millions of tons of carbon into the atmosphere. If Iowa refuses to reduce its reliance on biofuel production, there is plenty of evidence to support its direct responsibility for the impacts of climate change.

Located in the heart of the Corn Belt, Iowan farmers' livelihood and greatest source of income is their annual crop yields. Annual crop yields are determined by the health of the soil; permeability, nutrients, and topsoil quality. With the advent of pipelines and carbon capture and storage (CCS), concerns have started to emerge within the farming community. Studies have shown that during the construction of pipelines, agricultural lands are susceptible to soil compaction, erosion, and overall land degradation. Pipeline companies such as Summit have stated that they will compensate farmers' crop loss for the first three years. Though this may seem like fair compensation, the long-term effects of compaction on soil health outweigh that of temporary crop loss reimbursement. Destruction of agricultural lands, even for a good cause, will

only lead to monetary problems for farmers and the potential for increased water pollution and soil erosion.

When considering the justice implications of pipeline implementation at the local level, it is crucial to understand the procedural elements of pipeline permitting and the subsequent land acquisition process. Put shortly, the permitting process begins with informational meetings with landowners, continues with an initial petition to permit the pipeline through the IUB (Iowa Utilities Board), and concludes with an evidentiary hearing involving stakeholders conducted by the IUB. In regard to the land acquisition process, there are two main ways pipeline companies can acquire land: voluntary negotiation and eminent domain. Throughout the permitting process, pipeline companies are allowed to voluntarily negotiate easements with landowners. On the other hand, eminent domain can only be exercised once the pipelines are approved by the IUB.

II. The National Context

Prepared by Adrienne Clefisch, August Halverson, Ben Houry, Riley Marble, Margaret Mullin, and Ben Rotto

Considering the justness of implementing carbon capture technology at a national scale is an extremely complex and layered endeavor that requires multiple different perspectives. In order to understand if the pipelines in Iowa are environmentally just at the national level, it is important to look at the costs and benefits for Iowa in comparison to the greater U.S. We decided the main considerations that must be taken into account are balancing the focus on emission reduction versus carbon capture technology, transitioning the nation away from fossil fuels, federal treaties with Indigenous people, finding ways to incorporate all stakeholders in the decision making process, and the economic value of the ethanol industry. In examining these main ideas, we came to the conclusion that the carbon pipelines proposed in Iowa are not environmentally just at the national level.

In theory, the pipelines as they are proposed now are just in that they serve to decrease carbon emissions from the production of ethanol. As a huge emitter of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere, the U.S. has a large responsibility for where the world is at in terms of climate change and is morally obligated to address these issues. Furthermore, the U.S. has one of the most developed policy landscapes and capacity to use and regulate technological carbon dioxide removal which makes this a critical issue to address. Nevertheless, due to an overreliance on

public funding and an underutilization of the private sector, carbon capture pipelines often end up unfinished. When they are completed, pipelines have a history of dangerous leaks that threaten communities and public health. In regards to Indigenous treaties, the proposed Summit Carbon pipeline doesn't directly cross any federally recognized reservations but it comes into contact with many water sources in the same watersheds that reservations are on. A leak would jeopardize the livelihoods of Indigenous people and the natural resources they are closely connected to.

The purpose of the carbon pipelines is inherently linked with dependence on fossil fuels, something every nation needs to be moving away from. The pipelines serve as a lifeline to the ethanol industry, which holds the U.S. back in terms of clean energy and emission reductions investments. The ethanol industry needs the tax credits supporting the pipelines would give them under the Biden Administration's new climate legislation. Even if the ethanol industry reaches net zero emissions by 2030, ethanol post-production will be used in conjunction with fossil fuels. On the national level, the ethanol industry is not worth the environmental risk. It only accounts for a fifth of a percent of the GDP, and even less of a percentage of jobs in the country. Because the pipelines have such a direct connection to the polluting industry in question, it is necessary to reassess responsibility. The federal government is responsible for regulating and controlling industries and by extension their emissions.

The pipelines proposed in Iowa are not environmentally just at the national level because it continues the survival of the ethanol industry which is outdated and does not serve where the U.S. is headed in terms of a more sustainable, clean energy powered future. The risks posed to communities where the pipelines would be are too great for the possibility of limited effectiveness and the exclusive decision making table does not adequately consider the landowners and local communities' interests. Looking forward, more environmentally just alternatives involve storage or injection on site to limit the need for pipelines and reevaluating our climate goals at the federal level to focus more on emission reduction.

III. The Global Perspective

Prepared by Matt Bell, Tallulah Campbell, Steven Conradt, Jackson Geadelmann, and Betsy Gebhard

From the perspective of global environmental justice, the Iowa carbon sequestration pipelines are not environmentally just. Based on our research into the history, international treaties and global politics, safety and risk, and ethics of carbon sequestration pipelines, we have determined that there are more environmentally just solutions to managing carbon emissions.

While it is the responsibility of the United States to take on responsibility for carbon pollution given the contribution to global emissions that the US makes every year, the carbon pipeline is not the ethical way to do this. The main concern from an ethical perspective is the opportunity for global super polluters like the US to weaponize carbon sequestration pipelines to avoid decreasing emissions and other concrete climate action. These pipelines are advertised as storage solutions to manage the current US emissions instead of aiding the decrease of emissions globally. For other nations who don't have the financial capacity or physical capacity to develop sequestration infrastructure, this emissions loophole is not accessible and the burden of responsibility is shifted because the US is already "doing their part," in essence negating the idea of polluter pays methodology that seems ethical and just in the first place.

Some environmental justice advocates are also concerned that the implementation of carbon pipelines would increase the global north-south divide. The idea of the global north and global south divide resides around the thought that the nations north of the equator are better off financially than the countries south of the equator. This divide causes human rights concerns (countries that do not have worker protection laws, the right to protest, and environmental protections) and economic concerns. Some political scientists believe that labor may be exported to countries that do not have worker protection laws, and minimal environmental protection laws. Some also argue that some countries will not address environmental concerns such as poor maintenance and failing to address environmental concerns, citing economic factors as the motive for lack of oversight.

Yet even within the global north, CCS technologies present a number of safety risks. Severe weather events such as mudslides—as was the case in Satartia, Mississippi— earthquakes, and tornadoes, can all bring devastating impacts on CCS installations and in turn harm people and the environment. CCS technology and the geologic reservoirs in which extracted CO₂ is stored are fragile and are conducive to these sorts of catastrophe, especially amid an ever-warming climate. CCS is an attempt to fix global warming without addressing its primary driver. There are no shortcuts to reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. This is one of the only truly global threads between different countries' CCS efforts: CCS is dangerous, fails to address underlying issues of climate degradation, and again fails to hold oil and natural gas companies accountable for their actions.

On top of the safety concerns, there are greater questions challenging established international principles of justice. The United States is not a signatory to many significant pieces of international conventions relating to environmental protection, and from the international justice perspective, these pipelines pose a serious threat to environmental safety and integrity. Five principles of international law are particularly jeopardized by CCS and CDR projects, including:

1. The right to information access and to procedural justice (Aarhus Convention – 1998),
2. The responsibility to protect the environment is not equal (The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change – 1992),
3. There is a need to incentivize economic shift to sustainability (The Kyoto Protocol – 1997),
4. There is a need for conservation, sustainability, and sharing of resources (Convention on Biological Diversity – 1992), and
5. There is a right to be protected from hazardous waste (Basel Convention – 1990)

On the whole, wealthy countries have long histories of emitting massive amounts of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. Global policies and international law have done little to hold those responsible accountable for their actions. Despite being a tempting solution to slow down the climate crisis, carbon pipelines pose significant risks to health and safety, and their implementation presents numerous ethical and justice issues. Carbon pipelines—regardless of where they are—are unjust to everyone and fail to address the underlying causes of global warming.

IV. Intergenerational Justice

Prepared by Colton Baldus, Gabe Geoddeke, Ethan Holbert, Sidney Miller, Izzy Pippert, and Julia Schleicher

The basis of intergenerational environmental justice has aided the conversation surrounding the preservation of our planet and its natural resources to protect future generations, but it is not a foolproof argument. Policymakers must juggle with the idea that they have the capability to protect both current and future generations from the effects of climate change. There is no

one-size-fits-all approach to solving climate change, so the questions typically boil down to: “Who or what does this protect?”, “How will it protect?”, and “How much time and money is needed to achieve this plan?” The intergenerational justice framework aims to give people equitable opportunities, and future generations can benefit from a sustainable environmental future. As the time is running out to prevent more severe climate repercussions, the current generations need to decide now if they should be held accountable for climate mitigation efforts. Action is needed to protect future generations, and it is going to take a unified effort to achieve a just and equitable future.

Meanwhile, the topic of intergenerational justice is one that, when we address it, we often think about it as concerning our future generations, our children and grandchildren. This is no less true for Native Americans. For them, the idea of intergenerational justice can also take on deeper cultural meaning; the reason that native americans have a special stake in the topic of intergenerational justice is because specific land and species are important parts of their culture that are at risk of being lost or moved outside of reservation boundaries.

In an article from Michigan state, their associate professor of community sustainability, Kyle Whyte asserts that “Tribes are susceptible to loss of cultural, spiritual and economic relations to species such as moose or salmon as habitats change occur faster because their reservations are too small or fragmented to allow indigenous communities to follow the species’ movements to more suitable ecosystems”.

This ultimately stems from a historical issue. The genocide and stealing of land from Native Americans is the whole reason that the current problems exist with the potential loss of culture for Native Americans. Consequently, the US has a duty to protect these species and lands for Native Americans as, according to the article by Whyte, “US treaties are supposed to guarantee continued tribal access to the species even when they change location or their habitats are threatened by environmental stressors”.

The lack of federal checks against this project, especially with this knowledge, is concerning. According to Dennis Wamsted, an energy analyst at the Institute for Energy Economics and Financial Analysis, “There isn’t really enough experience with these pipelines to be able to say they’ll be safe going forward for five years, or 10 years or 15 years”; there is a promise in a legal treaty that guarantees the tribes these benefits for the future. This is reminiscent of a trust—the beneficiary being the tribes and the trustee being the Federal government. If we consider this promise in the treaty as a trust agreement, then this agreement entitles future members of that

tribe to the same benefits. With the knowledge in mind that treaty rights are potentially in jeopardy, intergenerational justice becomes even more important for the beneficiaries.

The Summit pipeline being proposed in the American midwest is a point of contention for many and people opposing it have found unlikely allies in their struggle. White farmers and landowners are taking the same side as Native Americans in this fight, which is in contrast to the issues with pipeline projects only a few years earlier. Many natives compare this situation to the Dakota Access pipeline a few years ago. The concern that natives have for their land is hinged on both the protection of it for future generations and protection of their culture as a whole, which is connected to the land. At a recent forum hosted by the Great Plains Action Society, native leaders asserted concerns the pipelines “could also affect water and other resources for Indigenous communities, even if the pipes run near their lands and not through them”. Summit assures the protesters of the pipeline that it is safe, but their concerns persist.

Intergenerational justice is especially important and relevant in Native American communities. The protection of cultural resources are at stake and the continuation of that culture in future generations could also be under threat. The pipeline proposes a unique question of whether it is just to help a small group of people preserve their livelihood, or to help support the cleanup of the environment for everyone. A compromise between these two is necessary and proper in order to respect and consider all the parties involved. Summit could consider more testing and safety precautions in their pipeline and the local and state governments could check up on them. Preserving the cultural land and resources for the tribes is a duty of the US government and it should be a priority that is of equal importance to the benefits that the pipeline could create.

The past has shown us the potential benefits and dangers of pipelines. It is important to understand that the decision we make on pipelines today will affect future generations in one way or another. The future is what we should think about when we agree to start building more pipelines. It is up to the present generation to safeguard the future generations by making decisions with the future generations’ potential problems in mind. If we continue down this short-sighted path of only doing what is best for the here and now, the problems faced by future generations will be too big to overcome. We can protect our future by remembering and learning from our past mistakes. If we can learn from these mistakes we can put ourselves in the best position now to ensure that future generations are not stuck cleaning up the mess we have created. It is also important to consider the idea that pipelines are not the future. Pipelines have great risk, and perhaps it is up to our generation now to come up with a cleaner more efficient system of energy.

Conclusion

The proposed pipelines do offer some relief to carbon pollution and avenue to make a more “green” energy grid, but they are nonetheless controversial. The conclusions that each group drew were based on weeks of research and writing, and represent the complexity of the situation; climate and energy policy is complicated and involves a substantial amount of consideration in order to arrive at an opinion on the situation. The students of POLS:340 Environmental Justice & Law surmised that the proposals of Navigator CO2 Ventures, Summit Carbon Solutions, and Wolf Carbon Solutions are problematic, and necessitate a societal pursuit towards non-carbon-emitting energy sources and greener practices. At every level, justice concerns seem to outweigh the short-term benefits of carbon pipelines and carbon sequestration. To protect local communities, to lead the United States down a more environmentally conscious path, to adhere to international principles of justice, and to ensure the health and wellbeing of future generations, the pipeline projects should not continue.